

Towards a roadmap for EU Agricultural Soil Management

Guidelines for work package 2

task 2.3

Identification of barriers and opportunities by scenario development

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Task 2.3 Identification of barriers and opportunities by scenario development

1. OBJECTIVE

The European Joint Program SOIL aims to create an integrated framework for soil research in Europe, to support harmonization of capacity, capability and knowledge for all Member States (MS), in order to enable all countries to use the knowledge on soil to face the global challenges. The program objective is to reduce the fragmentation of research to enhance agricultural soils potential to contribute to climate change adaptation and mitigation, while preserving productivity and environmental functions.

The soil knowledge has to be developed, shared and transferred, stored and organised, and applied, and task 2.3 activity aims to identify barriers to and opportunities for the enhancement of knowledge – development, sharing and transfer, organization and storage, application - on agricultural soils (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The knowledge process

Output of task 2.3 will contribute to the definition of the roadmap, a key tool to support strategic decision making for science, policy and implementation issues.

2. GUIDELINES FOR THE IDENTIFICATION OF BARRIERS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR SOIL KNOWLEDGE - TASK 2.3

2.1 METHODS

Data collection for the assessment of barriers to, and opportunities for soil knowledge will be organised at national level. To acquire the relevant necessary information, it has been considered appropriate not to propose from our side predefined questionnaires, with rigid fields and predetermined answers, but to design the survey in order to let the ideas and opinions of stakeholders on the topics emerge. In fact, for each country there are differences in sensitivities, cultures and social features, and national teams can exploit at best their knowledge on the stakeholder community. Furthermore, translating questionnaires in each native language often demonstrated to be a very sensitive process. Therefore, we recommend that each national team defines the most appropriate way to collect the data. At the end of the process, based on the survey, the national teams will report back the results on the tool provided, created and managed by CREA, that will guide the survey. Tips are added to help stakeholders during the interview, but they should be considered only as suggestions. The limitations imposed by the Corona virus could slow the collection of information, hence we suggest using all available means as questionnaires, phone interviews, Skype or similar tools, web meetings, email, and to start as soon as possible. Using videos, tutorials and webinars to illustrate the program and to help retrieve the information might be considered. A schematic view of Task 2.3 is reported in Fig. 2.

We suggest conducting the survey to at least 15-20 individuals. It could be useful to divide stakeholders in 3-4 categories such as: managing authorities, scientists, evaluators/technicians, farmers (farmers associations). Other categories might be included depending on the country.

The deadline for the compilation of the online tool is the 31st of July.

How to get the best results from your survey

In order to get the right information and to be able to convey your Country's information by using the tool provided, we suggest following the steps indicated below:

PRELIMINARY ACTION

The procedures proposed in the following guidelines must be validated by the key-contact person of each MSs by the 10th of May. Comments and proposal modification should be sent to roberta.farina@crea.gov.it.

STEP 1: PREPARATION OF THE QUESTIONNAIRES/INTERVIEWS/WEB MEETINGS

Who: each MS team.

Timing: by the 30th of May.

Objective: to define the format and content of the questionnaires/interviews/web meetings.

Description: this activity includes the preparation of the questionnaire/interviews/web meetings. The submission of questionnaires to stakeholders might be accompanied by leaflets or information sheets with the objectives and the main information on EJP-Soil.

Output: a consolidated version of the most important questions for the stakeholders.

STEP 2: PREPARATION OF THE SURVEY

Who: each MS team.

Timing: by the 30th of May.

Objective: this activity aims to set up all tools for the interviews/questionnaires.

Description: this activity includes the logistic set up of the survey. As already indicated, face-to-face workshops are probably not feasible in most countries. The following options should be used: 1) phone/web interviews, 2) online consultation; 3) workshops in web-conferences. The operational tool to be used should be tailored to the type of stakeholders involved.

Output: tools ready to start the collection of data.

STEP 3: SELECTION OF THE STAKEHOLDERS TO THE SURVEY

Who: Each MS teams in collaboration with WP9.

Timing: By the 30th of May.

Objective: To prepare the list of stakeholders.

Description: The selection of participants to the survey is essential for its success. We suggest following the multi-actor approach by engaging relevant and influencing actors. Identifying stakeholders, differentiating and categorising them is important to represent as much as possible the multifaceted world of soil knowledge. This selection will be made according to WP9. We suggest ensuring representativeness of all categories; and considering the technical/scientific capability to tailor the interviews.

Output: List of stakeholders per MS (defined by category such as: evaluators, Managing Authorities, technician, scientist, etc...).

STEP 4 CARRY ON THE SURVEY

Who: Each MS team for task 2.3.

Timing: By the 10th of July.

Objective: To acquire information.

Description: See the template.

Output: Internal report with all information acquired.

STEP 5. REPORTING RESULTS OF SURVEY

Who: Each MS team for task 2.3.

Timing: By the 31st of July.

Objective: To organize and report the results of the survey.

Description: An online tool (template) will be prepared by CREA (in English) for the upload of information by the national representatives.

Output: Template filled in with all information required

Fig. 2 Schematic view of the Task 2.3 Identification of barriers and opportunities by scenario development

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 652615.

3. TEMPLATE FOR REPORTING ON BARRIERS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR SOIL KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPMENT AND USE

Fig. 3 Template for Member State (MS) data upload

EJP SOIL Task 2.3 - Identification of barriers and opportunities by scenario development	
REPORT of SINGLE MEMBER STATE	
Instruction	
1) The aim of this document is to collect data derived from Member State survey to create a Task2.3 database as homogeneous as possible.	
2) How to fill this file: Per each Environmental zone you have information, you are required to compile one Excel file. So, if you have information of 2 zones, you have to send us two separate files. Please rename the file as follow: Country name_environmental code.xls (e.g. Italy_MS.xls)	
3) This file is divided in several spreadsheets named with the same letters used in the description section of the Guidelines (i.e., A, B, etc.). This is to maintain the correspondence with the information requested in the document.	
4) In section A, please insert the general information about your Country.	
5) In section B, please insert all the data about the interviewed stakeholders. In each cell, select directly from a list.	
6) In section C, please include the barriers and opportunities related to the knowledge compartment. In the cells, you have two options: select directly from a list or insert manually your data.	
7) The section D is divided in several sub-sections (i.e., D, D1, D2, etc.): "D" corresponds to the question 19 of the section D of the guideline, while "D1, D2, etc.," correspond to the other questions replicated for the different soil challenges. For the most relevant soil challenges, please compile sheet D1, D2, etc. You (as country contact) are allowed to insert other spreadsheets if the most relevant soil challenges are more than 5.	
8) In the cells of each section, you have two options: select directly from a list or insert manually your data. In sections "C" and "D", you can write directly your answer or select from a list, where some "tips" are listed.	
For information you can contact silvia.vanino@crea.gov.it	
This document is part of EJP SOIL . This programme has received funding from EU Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 652615.	

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The diagram illustrates the process flow: EJP SOIL TARGETS (Climate change mitigation, Greenhouse gas emissions reduction, Soil erosion control, Soil conservation) feed into Development (Transfer & sharing, Harmonization, organization & storage, Application). This leads to National Farm Survey and National Farms Survey, which identify Barriers and opportunities from each knowledge compartment. These then lead to ACHIEVE EJP-SOIL TARGETS (via Section C: Content development on the knowledge compartment to reach targets) and ACHIEVE SOIL CHALLENGES ASPIRATIONS (via Section D: Participation on the relevant soil challenges). SOIL CHALLENGES ASPIRATIONS include: Water storage capacity (improving), Nutrient retention or use efficiency (improving), Soil indicators (improving), Disease resistance (improving), Soil erosion (controlling), Erosion control (avoid/delay) (controlling), Salinization and acidification (controlling), Soil sealing (controlling), and Soil compaction (controlling).

A) GENERAL INFORMATION

- 1 Name of the Member State (select from dropdown list)
- 2 Which environmental zones are relevant to consider in your country (select, from the dropdown list, the relevant zones for the country). Please prepare a file for each zone.
- 3 How many stakeholders did you interview for this exercise (indicate the number)
- 4 Please illustrate the criteria of stakeholders selection (max 500 words)

Fig. 5. Template Section B) Information for each interviewed stakeholder

Insert all the data about the interviewed stakeholders							
#	Gender	Age	Level of education	Stakeholder group	Interview type	1 Relevant soil challenges	2 Relevant soil challenges
1	Female	41-54	University	Farmer/Farmers association	web-call	Soil organic matter & peat soil conservation (improving)	
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C) GENERAL INFORMATION ON SOIL KNOWLEDGE COMPARTMENT IN YOUR COUNTRY

To inquire separately for each compartment of knowledge (template questions from 11 to 18) might require an excessive time for some or most of the stakeholders. You can group knowledge compartments in only one question. However, keep in mind that to allow for a complete exploration of the barriers/opportunities, you must report results separately for each compartment.

11 According to stakeholders, which are the most important general barriers, at national level, to knowledge development, perceived as obstacles to reach the main EJP goals? (List and prioritisation of barriers; relevant observations and comments, max 500 words)

Tips: For this compartment, you can refer to critical aspects related to the main actors/processes of knowledge development, namely universities & education systems, research organizations, but also advisory services, farmers, consumers. Critical aspects might be: the identification of research needs is not effective, as a result research is not focusing on the most important topics; too large number of soil research institutions whose actions are fragmented and not coordinated; institutions working on soil science are not enough; scientific equipment in university/research organizations are obsolete; financial resources allocated

to soil research are not sufficient; selection processes mechanisms for research project are not appropriate, bottlenecks and lack of coordination among national/regional institutions (ministries, regions and national agencies) within the research chain; lack of public-private partnership on soil research; lack of relations among research, advisory services and farmers (including their associations); lack of training for advisors and farmers on soil-related issues. In the survey also other drivers out of the knowledge compartment, such as economic constraints, institutional/regulatory political bottlenecks and limitations, social, cultural, gender and gaps, might be mentioned.

12 According to stakeholders, which opportunities are offered by soil knowledge development to reach the main EJP goals at country level? (List and prioritisation of general opportunities in knowledge development, relevant observations and comments, max 500 words)

Tips: As seen for knowledge development barriers, you can list and describe the opportunities offered by the development of new knowledge at national level. In this case opportunities can come from elements such as: promoting start-ups; increasing funding for soil related research; increasing the number and improving curricula of the soil science students; increasing training for farmers, advisors and other actors potentially involved in developing soil-related knowledge; promoting women participation to soil research; supporting multi- and trans-disciplinary research; supporting multi-actor projects (better involvement of farmers/advisors in the early stages of projects definition might boost more appropriate definition of research needs), activate/valorise/fund long term experiments; switch from top-down to bottom-up research, etc.

13 According to stakeholders, which are the general barriers/gaps to knowledge sharing and transfer perceived as obstacles to reach the main EJP goals? (List and prioritisation of issues in knowledge sharing and transfer, relevant observations and comments, max 500 words)

Tips: Barriers in this compartment at general level typically refer to critical aspects related to the sharing and transfer of knowledge by the main actors/processes, namely universities & education systems, involved in the development of new knowledge, to the stakeholders in the broadest sense. Processes of knowledge transfer and sharing that might happen among farmers, advisors, practitioners should also be considered (operational groups implemented within the EIP AGRI, as well as multi-actor projects funded under H2020 could be examples). Furthermore, when considering knowledge sharing it could be worth to distinguish between sharing with farmers/practitioners/advisors from the dissemination of knowledge to the civil society. Barriers identified in this step could be: networks science-science, science-farmers, science-advisors, science-society, science-policy are not established; communication between researchers and farmers is not effective and this hampers the transfer of useful knowledge; lack of training for farmers and advisors; lack of training for researchers on how better communicate with practitioners; difficult access to proper advice for

farmers; dissemination is missing, dissemination content does not convey useful information, communication is not clear for all stakeholder categories, etc.

14 According to stakeholders, which opportunities at general level are offered by knowledge sharing and transfer? (List and prioritisation of opportunities; relevant observations and comments, max 500 words)

Tips: Opportunities in knowledge sharing and transfer at country level typically refer to the valorisation of knowledge from universities & education systems, involving stakeholders. Sharing and transfer of knowledge between farmers and advisors should also be considered. Opportunities might be: establishment of permanent national networks science-science, science-farmers, science advisors, science-society, science-policy; improving training programmes for farmers and advisors; supporting peer-to-peer training between farmers/advisors; supporting the setting-up of demonstration activities (e.g. experimental and demonstration farms); supporting multi-actor approach, particularly the exchange between researchers and farmers/advisors; improving dissemination activity; making dissemination mandatory in all funded projects; allowing for targeted and effective dissemination; using effective communication to increase awareness on the importance of soil in all of society, etc.

15 According to stakeholders, which are the most important general barriers to harmonization, organization and storage of information about soil-related knowledge, perceived as obstacles to reach the main EJP goals? (List and prioritisation of barriers; relevant observations and comments, max 500 words)

Tips: For this topic, you can refer to the main general barriers affecting knowledge harmonization, organization, and storage of soil information. In this case barriers might deploy their negative effects at different levels. (i) Barriers on soil data might be: outdated information, different methodologies used for soil sampling, analysis and mapping, and/or storage data dispersed and often not available to the public; (ii) barriers on data sharing might be lack of common data policy and data fragmentation; (iii) technological barriers might be lack of internet access in rural areas, lacking common “decision support” ICT tools able to secure soil data storage facilities at EU level.

16 According to stakeholders, which are the opportunities offered by harmonization, organization and storage of information about soil-related knowledge, to reach the main EJP goals?

Tips: You can list and describe the opportunities offered by the harmonization, organization and storage of information about soil-related knowledge (both already existing and new) at national level. Opportunities to overcome current soil data fragmentation might be promotion of harmonization and standardization methodologies; creation of national infrastructures and interactive web-based communication of soil data; data storage with international standards, etc. Another opportunity can be the validation and integration of large data sets by using new developments in information technology such as geographic information

systems, statistics and modelling, contributing to reporting on the international commitments (Kyoto protocol, UNFCCC, CAP).

17 According to stakeholders, which are the most important general barriers to knowledge application perceived as obstacles to reach the main EJP goals? (List and prioritisation of barriers; relevant observations and comments, max 500 words)

Tips: In knowledge application you can refer to four main general barriers: economic, socio-cultural, institutional and technological. These barriers operate from the scale of individuals/communities through to the global scale. Economic barriers can be costs and lags in return from changing land management practices, yields and profits may not respond as farmer/land managers expect; lack of appropriate incentives. Social barriers can be lack of communication structure in which dissemination, communication and knowledge exchange activities are facilitated (i.e. lack of soil specific website, popular articles, soil guidelines...) or/and communities pressure/traditional practices and gender norms that can hinder change of soil management practices. Institutional and legal barriers can affect implementation of sustainable soil management practices as well as land tenure and access; lack of good policies and incentives; lack of scientific support to policy makers and/or vice versa. Technological barriers can be lack of internet access in rural areas, lacking “decision support” ICT tools, lack of applied agricultural technology. In addition to these four main categories of barriers, it should also be considered the lack of exchange, often reported, between researchers and farmers/advisors. Correct application of knowledge and research results require specific capacities that often farmers or advisors do not possess. The lack of tools that facilitate positive exchanges among farmers and researchers, or among farmers (peer-to peer) might represent an important barrier to applying knowledge already developed and tested.

18 According to stakeholders, which are the opportunities offered by soil knowledge application to reach the main EJP goals?

Tips: As seen before, you can list and describe the opportunities offered by the application of new knowledge at national level: soils are better integrated in the circular economy and bio-economy with a good consequence in farms profits; good policies and incentives with effective policy measures; development of region-specific soil management strategies; farmers have adequate ICT tools and use them; the existence of specific mechanisms to support farmers in applying this knowledge (access to training and advice, demonstration activities, field visits, etc.).

Fig. 6. Template Section C) General information on soil knowledge compartments in your country

Include the barriers and opportunities related to the knowledge compartment giving a priority. Select directly from a list or insert manually your data in the option "Other".

Priority	11-According to stakeholders, which are the most important general barriers, at national level, to knowledge development, perceived as obstacles to reach the main EJP goals?	12-According to stakeholders, which opportunities are offered by soil knowledge development to reach the main EJP goals at country level?	13- According to stakeholders, which are the general barriers to knowledge sharing and transfer perceived as obstacles to reach the main EJP goals?	14-According to stakeholders, which opportunities at general level are offered by knowledge sharing and transfer?	15-According to stakeholders, which are the most important general barriers to harmonization, organization and storage of information about soil-related knowledge perceived as obstacles to reach the main EJP goals? If other, write here	16-According to stakeholders, which opportunities by harmonization, organization and storage of information about soil-related knowledge, to reach the main EJP goals?
1	too large number of soil research institutions and actions for	increasing funding for soil related research	dissemination is missing	making dissemination mandatory		
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Notes/Comment (max 200 words)						

Read_me_first | A) General information | B) Info interviewed stakeholder | **C) Barriers Opportunities knowle** | D) Soil challenges | D1_Name soil challenge1 | D2_Name soil C ...

D) INFORMATION FOR THE RELEVANT SOIL CHALLENGES ASPIRATION (LIMIT THIS PART OF SURVEY TO THE MOST RELEVANT CHALLENGES). FOR EACH RELEVANT CHALLENGE:

As for session C), to inquire separately for each compartment of knowledge (template questions from 20 to 27), might require an excessive time for some or most of the stakeholders. You can group all the knowledge compartments in only one question for each relevant soil challenge aspiration. However, in order to allow for a complete exploration of the barriers/opportunities, you might report results separately for each compartment.

19 According to stakeholders, what is the relevance of each soil challenge for the achievement of the main EJP-SOIL goals (from dropdown list: None, Low relevant, Medium relevant, High relevant)

Tips: *Opportunities focusing on soil science development could be represented by the identification of research needs (topics) in the soil challenge or be of the type: evaluation of the connection between the land use and the [name of the challenge]; development and application of soil sustainable management indicators; development and validation of relevant bio-physical models for predicting the long term dynamics of soil phenomena; measuring at local level and predicting/extrapolate at landscape and regional scale, and can be also more detailed for local knowledge needs. Other opportunities can descend from specific regulations, agro-environmental measures at national and regional level, country or regional incentives.*

22 According to stakeholders, which are the most important barriers/gaps to sharing and transfer knowledge perceived as obstacles to overcome [name of the challenge] in this country? (List and prioritisation of barriers in knowledge sharing and transfer, relevant observations and comments, max 500 words)

Tips: *In the template you can describe the barriers to knowledge sharing and transfer with a specific focus to soil knowledge which hinders the overcoming of [name of the challenge]. Possible issues in knowledge sharing and transfer specific to the soil can be of the type: there is knowledge on the issue, but it is not disseminated, the knowledge is not available for all actors involved in soil; there is no communication among all stakeholders; there are not appropriate methods to support an effective sharing among researchers and farmers; etc.*

23 According to stakeholders, which are the opportunities offered by knowledge sharing and transfer for the soil challenge [name of the challenge]? (List of opportunities; relevant observations and comments, max 500 words)

Tips: *Opportunities to overcome the soil challenge might be: availability of knowledge for stakeholders; capacity building from universities and schools; technical networks science-farmers; establishing soil networks for scientists, science-policy and science-society; improving dissemination; continuous knowledge synthesis and feedback loop; stakeholder participation; setting-up operational groups and taking stock from those already working on soil-related themes; strengthening scientific capacities and cooperation; setting-up capacity building programmes for young soil scientists and societal stakeholders i.e. farmers and advisors, policy makers, landowners and managers, civil society and industry.*

24 According to stakeholders, which are the most important barriers/gaps to knowledge harmonization, organization and storage (i.e. soil data acquisition, organization in open soil data base, georeferencing of soil properties, standard protocols for soil analyses, sharing long term experiment data) perceived as obstacles to overcome the challenge [name of the challenge]? (List and prioritisation of barriers; relevant observations and comments, max 500 words)

Tips: *In the template you can describe the barriers to data harmonization, organization and storage with a specific focus on [name of the challenge]. Possible issues specific to the soil are: lack of harmonization and standardization in data collected over time; common methodologies used for soil sampling; analysis and mapping; data fragmentation; integrated framework and ICT tools to secure soil data storage facilities at different levels. Application of specific knowledge management, common tools, organizational learning can overcome the current fragmentation.*

25 According to stakeholders, which are the opportunities offered by knowledge harmonization, organization and storage for soil challenge [name of the challenge]? (List of opportunities; relevant observations and comments, max 500 words)

Tips: *For [name of the challenge], opportunities focusing on data harmonization, organization and data storage can be related to the standardization of methodologies with international standards and accepted procedures, the interactive web-based communication of soil data. Other opportunities can descend from specific regulations, agro-environmental measures at national and regional level, country or regional incentives.*

26 According to stakeholders, which are the most important barriers/gaps, at national level, to knowledge application perceived as obstacles to overcome the challenge [name of the challenge]? (List and prioritisation of barriers; relevant observations and comments, max 500 words)

Tips: *In the template you can describe the barriers to knowledge application with a specific focus to [name of the challenge]. Possible issues in knowledge application specific for the soil are: lack of technologies, ICT tools and DSS (Decision Support Systems); willingness of farmer to apply new soil management practices; farmer loss yield and profit; lack of specific regulations and EU Policies; barriers to adoption and enabling conditions to implement soil challenge; etc.*

27 According to stakeholders, which are the opportunities offered by knowledge application for soil challenge [name of the challenge]? (List of opportunities; relevant observations and comments, max 500 words)

Tips: *Opportunities of the application of knowledge can be: improving thematic guidelines (water, nutrient and fertilizer...); certification principles for tools and advisory services; ready-to-use technologies, openness and contact between the soil science community and society; good interfacing between science and policy; improving access to long-term field sites and development of specific advice; ICT decision support system; good specific policies and incentives, address future policy needs for new knowledge; facilitate knowledge sharing and mutual learning science-society-policy.*

Fig. 8. Template section D) Information for each relevant soil challenge

For the most relevant soil challenges, rename the spreadsheets and insert barriers and opportunities giving a priority			
Priority	20- According to stakeholders, which are the most important general barriers and gaps, at national level, in the actual knowledge development, which are perceived as obstacles to overcome the challenge "Name Soil Challenge"?	21- According to stakeholders, which are the opportunities offered by soil knowledge development for the challenge "Name Soil Challenge"?	22 According to stakeholders, which transfer knowledge perceived as obstacle?
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E) FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

28 According to stakeholders, which are the other drivers/constraint/opportunities (economic, social, policy, others) influencing the achievement of the soil challenge? (max 500 words)

29 Could you briefly report about the different perceptions of stakeholders' groups on the different topics? (max 500 words)

30 And in your opinion, what is the reason for the different perceptions - age, level of education, profession, field of activity, other? (max 500 words)

Fig. 9. Template for section E) Final considerations

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
28 According to stakeholders, which are the other drivers/constraint/opportunities (economic, social, policy, others) influencing the achievement of the soil challenge? (max 500 words)	29 Could you briefly report about the different perceptions of stakeholders' groups on the different topics? (max 500 words)	30 And in your opinion, what is the reason for the different perceptions - age, level of education, profession, field of activity, other? (max 500 words)								
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